

Attitudes and behaviours of mental health professionals in the care of transgender people: A qualitative study

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Accessible Summary

What is known on the subject?

- Mental health professionals' beliefs about transgender individuals vary, often influenced by stereotypes.
- There's recognition of healthcare needs, but limited knowledge impacts decision-making.
- Stereotypes persist regarding why transgender individuals seek mental health care.

What the paper adds to existing knowledge?

- Professionals' attitudes show both positive support and negative, discriminatory views.
- Lack of training and knowledge gaps hinder effective care for transgender individuals.
- Pathologising attitudes exist, associating gender diversity with mental health conditions.

What Are the implications for practice?

- Addressing training gaps is crucial for equitable care for transgender individuals.
- Challenging stereotypes and beliefs is necessary to reduce stigma and improve understanding.
- Enhancing knowledge and evidence-based tools will ensure safe and equal health-care access.

Abstract

Introduction: Transgender people face against significant barriers in accessing mental health services due to, among other reasons, discrimination and a lack of expertise among professionals.

Aim: To explore the beliefs and attitudes of professionals in the mental health network of the region of Murcia towards transgender people, focusing on aspects such as knowledge, perceptions, and prejudices about gender identity.

Method: We carried out a qualitative study involving 14 participants, conducting semi-structured interviews based on prior knowledge of the topic. We asked the

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professionals about their experiences and challenges in their clinical interaction with transgender users and followed an inductive-deductive process to analyse the data.

Results: Two main themes were identified from the interviews, which were sub-categorised into different sub-themes: (a) beliefs about transgender people: underlying factors and origins of gender diversity, health needs, and stereotypes about the demand for health care; (b) attitudes and behaviours of professionals towards transgender people: pathologization and attitudes towards decision-making.

Discussion/Implications for Practice: Our findings suggest that mental health professionals tend to oversimplify the factors underlying gender diversity and hold certain stereotypical beliefs about these users that oversimplify the complexity of their experiences.

KEYWORDS

attitudes, mental health professionals, stereotypes, stigma, transgender

1 | INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there have been significant advances in acknowledging the rights of transgender and gender diverse (TGD) individuals (Coleman et al., 2022; Belmonte, 2020). Despite these advancements, concerns persist, as highlighted in the 2023 report from the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) in 2023, which identified a rise in hate speech and legislative measures that threaten LGBTI equality (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), 2023). Spain has seen recent legal strides with the enactment of [Law 4/2023](#) for real and effective equality of transgender individuals and to ensure the rights of LGBTI people (1 March 2023), which notably recognizes the right to gender self-determination for TGD individuals. However, its implementation has sparked considerable discord among various political factions, as well as within society and the media (Navarro Marchante, 2023). This discord extends into healthcare systems, where it is crucial to understand how health professionals deal with this evolving landscape (Abern & Maguire, 2018).

Consistent with minority stress theory (Meyer, 2003), transgender and gender diverse (TGD) individuals continue to face significant barriers in accessing healthcare services tailored to their needs due to transphobia and a lack of cultural sensitivity within the healthcare system (Aylagas-Crespillo et al., 2018; García-Acosta et al., 2020; Jiménez-Barbero et al., 2023). This lack of professional expertise may be detrimental to the overall health of transgender people. For instance, previous studies have condemned the discrimination faced by TGD people, pointing to higher rates of substance abuse, sexually transmitted infections, mental health issues, and overall poorer perceived health (Jaffee et al., 2016; Miller et al., 2023; Reisner et al., 2016). On the other hand, the importance of offering therapeutic environments that consider the individual needs of users is gaining prominence (von der Warth et al., 2023). To establish healthcare settings that are safe and respectful for transgender people, it is critical to examine the attitudes of professionals. These

attitudes, which are shaped by cognitive, affective, and behavioural components (Ajzen Ickek et al., 2018; Hirsch Adler, 2005), have a significant impact on the care delivered. In this context, a few authors have previously examined the factors that influence the attitudes of mental health professionals (Bolding et al., 2022; Canvin et al., 2022; Cutillas-Fernández et al., 2023; Miller et al., 2023). Their findings conclude that these attitudes are largely conditioned by individual factors, such as the professionals' personal interests, what gender ideology means to them, or certain socio-demographic variables. These include being a woman or having relationships with transgender people outside the professional sphere (Dispenza & O'Hara, 2016; Whitehead et al., 2012; Whitman & Han, 2017). Moreover, previous research suggests that training is the most effective means of changing these attitudes, thereby reducing negative attitudes, transphobia, and social distancing. This, in turn, improves users' access to the healthcare system (Clark et al., 2017; Tishelman et al., 2019; Torres et al., 2015).

Despite the progress made in understanding gender diversity, significant challenges remain when it comes to providing mental health care to transgender people. Lack of specialised training, lack of dedicated resources, and institutional resistance to change are all barriers that contribute to the perpetuation of negative attitudes and the failure to provide person-centred care (von der Warth et al., 2023). Gaining an understanding of professional attitudes and improving their methods of practice emerge as critical components of building an inclusive mental health system that meets the needs of this community in a respectful and compassionate manner.

Although issues relating to problems and barriers in the care of transgender people in mental health services are not new (McKeown & McCusker, 1995), this study aims to delve into the beliefs and attitudes of mental health professionals towards transgender people. We look at factors such as knowledge, perceptions, and prejudices about gender identity and how these may influence the health care provided to transgender people.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Study design

Using a hermeneutic approach, we conducted a qualitative study to explore the beliefs held by mental health professionals in their clinical interactions with transgender people. Our objective was to determine how these beliefs influence the attitudes and behaviours of mental health professionals toward these users. To this end, we used their interpretation of their own work experience as the basis for the research (Berenguera Ossó et al., 2014). In preparing this paper, we followed the Consolidated Criteria for Qualitative Research Reporting (COREQ) checklist (Tong et al., 2007).

2.2 | Participants

We used convenience sampling to construct the sample via an online survey and by drawing on the authors' professional networks. We set specific eligibility criteria for selection to ensure the relevance of the sample, as follows: (1) being an actively practising mental health professional at the time of the interview, (2) having completed their training (residency), and (3) practising at least part of their profession in the public sector. After the initial interviews, we expanded the sample using a snowball sampling method to broaden recruitment (Law, 2019).

We determined the sample size based on information saturation, following the guidelines established by Malterud et al. (2016). We contacted 17 participants, but three declined the invitation to participate, citing difficulties in finding time for the interview. This resulted in a final sample of 14 participants who met the selection criteria and agreed to be interviewed by the research team. With this sample, saturation of the theoretical data was reached earlier than expected, after the tenth interview. Nevertheless, we continued to conduct interviews to confirm this.

2.3 | Data collection procedure

The data collection technique used was the in-depth interview, which makes it possible to capture the meaning of the events, situations, and actions in which the participants are involved (Acosta et al., 2019; Carrizo, 2014; Maxwell, 2013).

For the development of the interviews, we developed a list of topics and guiding questions for the interview based on the scientific literature (Table 1) (Cutillas-Fernández et al., 2023).

The lead researcher arranged the interview locations based on the participants' preferences. The researcher responsible for conducting the interviews is a mental health professional. This is a help in approaching and recruiting participants, but also a problem when it comes to bringing her professional perspective into the interview process if not reflexively guarded against. Before the interviews themselves, we held informal discussions with the

TABLE 1 Semi-structured interview script.

Socio-demographics
Age, gender, sexual orientation, occupation, place of work, and whether or not they have transgender people in their immediate/family environment.
Attitudes and beliefs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In your opinion, what are the factors behind the transgender experience? • What are your thoughts on the statement 'Only two sexes are found in nature'? • In your opinion, what are the main health issues concerning the transgender community? • How would you say transgender identity affects the mental health of this community? • In your opinion, what is the main reason why a transgender person seeks access to the mental health system? • Outline the primary service that you (and your organization) provide to the transgender community. • Are there any stories in particular that you would like to share? • In your opinion, what are the specific mental health needs of the transgender community (as opposed to non-transgender people)?
Training and education
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Could you outline the training you've had with respect to gender and transgender health. This includes both at university and during your residency, provided by the institution. Feel free to add any training you have pursued independently. • Are you aware of the existence of any protocols in the region? • Are you aware of any person in your workplace who is responsible for/specialized in gender issues? • In your opinion, what are the key competencies required by a professional when working with a transgender person?
Accessibility
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List the measures that your organization is taking to improve access for transgender people. • How do you handle discussions with users regarding the use of pronouns and terms associated with gender identity? • When working with transgender people in the clinical setting, how do you deal with issues such as stigma and exclusion? Can you provide an example? • Would you say that the mental health professional's role should be to assist individuals in making decisions about their gender identity or to provide emotional support in the transition process? • Are you personally aware of a case of transition where the user was not satisfied? Please elaborate.

interviewees. The interviews lasted between 25 and 50 min and were recorded and transcribed verbatim. We took field notes during and at the end of each interview, and interviewer interference was strictly minimized. In this way, we ensured that the researcher played only a guiding role in the participants' statements. Participants were able to critically reflect on their experiences in retrospect, providing a thorough account of their lived experience in their clinical approach to transgender people seeking care in the mental healthcare system. Following each interview, the researcher engaged in a reflective process with the participants. This process involved paraphrasing and summarizing the interview content, along with asking for clarification to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the narrative.

2.4 | Data analysis

We used Atlas.ti software to process the data. For the analysis of the data, we followed the process of inductive and deductive analysis proposed by Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006). The analysis process started inductively by reading and re-reading the documents, and researchers compared them with one another to ensure reliability. The third step involved identifying themes. Beliefs about gender and transgender identity, stereotypes around the demand for care, and attitudes related to pathologization were prominent and recurring themes. This prompted us to conduct a more in-depth analysis based on the concepts previously explored in the literature review. The themes identified were compared inductively with the themes explored in the literature consulted to construct and redefine the themes and categories. We then turned our attention to the relationships and connections between the categories to see how they related to each other. These relationships were constructed using the framework of Fishbein and Ajzen's (1975) theory of reasoned action and Rosenstock's (1974) model of health beliefs. They propose that beliefs about the consequences of an action and evaluations of those consequences determine attitudes towards that action, which in turn influence the person's intention and actual behaviour. It has therefore been suggested that beliefs influence attitudes and attitudes influence behaviour. Each step of the analysis process was conducted independently by two researchers. The researchers who independently conducted the analysis were PhDs with expertise in qualitative analysis. One was from a mental health background and the other from a health science background. The second researcher was not from the mental health field to avoid the analysis being mediated by the work environment. We used triangulation to reach

consensus on the final structure of our findings. We then went back to the participants for feedback and confirmation of the results.

2.5 | Ethical considerations

The study was approved by the University of Murcia's Ethics Committee (Reg. No. CEI 3123). Before the interviews began, we explained the purpose of the study to each participant both verbally and in writing. We informed them that we required their consent to participate in the study, that they could withdraw at any time (including after the interview), and requested their permission to use a voice recorder. Furthermore, to protect the confidentiality of the interviewees, we assigned a code to each participant and removed any identifying information from the transcripts.

3 | RESULTS

We conducted 14 interviews with a range of mental health professionals, including four psychiatrists, four psychologists, three social workers, and three nurses (Table 2).

3.1 | Theme 1: Beliefs about transgender people that have an impact on the care they receive

Our analysis begins by defining belief as an assertion that a person considers to be true or real. This assertion may be related to events,

TABLE 2 Socio-occupational profile of participants.

Participant	Occupation	Place of work	Gender/LGBTQI+ education during training	Awareness of the region of Murcia's protocol
1	Psychology	Mental Health Center	No training	Yes
2	Psychology	Mental Health Center	No training	No
3	Psychology	Mental Health Center	Gender-based violence // Self-guided study	Yes
4	Nursing	Mental Health Center	No training	Yes
5	Psychiatry	CSM - IJ ^a	Gender training at university or during residency // Self-guided study	Yes
6	Social work	Mental Health Center	No training	Yes
7	Psychiatry	ETAC ^b	No training	
8	Social work	ETAC	Gender training, university and post-graduate level	No
9	Psychiatry	Mental Health Center	No training	No
10	Psychology	Mental Health Center	No training // Clinical experience	No
11	Nursing	UHP ^c	No training // Self-guided study	No
12	Social work	ETAC	Gender training	Yes
13	Psychiatry	Mental Health Center	Self-guided study	Yes
14	Psychology	Mental Health Center	Gender training	No

^aMental Health Center for Children and Young People (*Centro de Salud Mental - Infanto Juvenil*).

^bAssertive Communication Treatment Team (*Equipo de Tratamiento Asertivo Comunicativo*).

^cInpatient Psychiatric Unit (*Unidad de Hospitalización Psiquiátrica*).

values, religion, knowledge, or other factors. Throughout the interviews, we find beliefs that are rooted in fact and others that are based on stereotypes, leading to variations in perceptions of transgender care. Analysis of the interviews reveals beliefs concerning the origins of gender diversity, healthcare needs, and stereotypes associated with the demand for care.

3.1.1 | Underlying factors or origin of gender diversity

The professionals interviewed identified three main factors contributing to gender diversity: biological or genetic, psychological, and a final social aspect linked to greater visibility of the LGBTQI+ community or other factors related to socialization. Consequently, professionals tend to make a distinction between people they consider to be 'genuinely' transgender, attributing their identity to biological or genetic factors, and a second category associated with social and psychological factors. This leads to the idea (among some professionals) of an implicit relationship between the origin of gender diversity and the growing visibility of the LGBTQI+ community. This oversimplification, coupled with the separation of the transgender experience from the inherent plurality of human reality, may lead to the pathologization of this population.

It's not the same when a child of six or eight already has this feeling of distress with their own body, as when it happens as an adolescent. I think there's a distinction. I believe there is a difference because adolescence is already a time of much uncertainty, a lot of anger, of... trying out a lot of stuff... If you already have a clear idea beforehand, it is more pronounced...

Participant 7

3.1.2 | Healthcare needs

Most of the professionals interviewed were able to identify at least one healthcare need specific to transgender people. However, they also acknowledged their limited knowledge on the matter, which often leads them to make decisions based on assumptions or personal beliefs.

I reckon that there is still a lack of very clear protocols, specific facilities, or professionals with the right know-how to address their concerns. They bring up issues that, a lot of the time, even we professionals ourselves don't have straightforward answers for.

Participant 2

Some of the most commonly mentioned physical healthcare needs include hormone therapy, reproductive healthcare, and surgery, along with the potential repercussions of these procedures. However, in the end, many professionals reduce these healthcare needs to the

transition process alone. It should be noted that there is a tendency among some professionals to view the transition process as a stage in the health-illness continuum. As a consequence, there is an implicit perception that transgender people are 'cured' once they have successfully completed the process and undergone gender reassignment surgery.

So, well, I do think that they should start the process and see it through with all that it entails. But, let's be real, it's a very scary process because it means lots of changes and it's a huge adventure, you know?

Participant 3

In terms of mental health needs, professionals identified affective problems, such as anxiety and depression, and adjustment difficulties as the main reasons for seeking treatment. Participants traced these mental health issues back to the discrimination and stigma faced by these people throughout their lives, together with the uncertainty surrounding the transition process. They also pointed to social factors, such as family support, social status, and educational attainment, as key elements in making it easier to access health care during this process.

The mental struggle...the lack of acceptance from their environment. I think, at the end of the day, it's emotional stuff... anxiety, depression, stress... I'd say that's how it goes. It's partly because of that, because of what they go through during the whole transition until it's finally over, it's a very stressful process, really tough. I'd say that, sometimes, there's not much acceptance from the people around them.

Participant 1

Another commonly cited reason for seeking help has to do with symptoms associated with personality disorders and trauma. In these instances, professionals describe symptoms like impulsivity, self-harm, and conflicts with one's own identity that are hallmarks of these conditions. They also point to traumatic events in patients' lives, which vary in terms of their impact and severity.

There might indeed be some cases where this identity diffusion, for example, that you'd see in a personality disorder, could be to do with being transgender, and other cases where it's not...where the patient is transgender and also has identity diffusion, but it doesn't affect them.

Participant 9

People who are more erratic, more volatile. Besides this gender issue, there were other things... I mean, like, more problems in their life, in how they functioned as such. They didn't have jobs... I mean, they had lots more problems than just the gender issue.

Participant 1

Finally, the professionals refer to a third group of clients, often associated with psychotic disorders and autistic spectrum disorders, linking these diagnoses to the search for identity and gender identity conflicts.

A significant number of, especially transgender teens, show signs of autism and then there's another group with issues around emotional instability.

Participant 5

3.1.3 | Stereotypes around the demand for healthcare

The professionals interviewed often had a stereotypical perception of transgender people seeking care in the mental health system. In this regard, they paint a picture of a homogeneous user profile, possibly reflecting a limited understanding of the subjective experiences of this community. This stereotyped user profile is often associated with behaviours typical of adolescence and issues related to the construction of identity and personal autonomy.

When it has nothing to do with a relationship with someone else, but it's like you're in some sort of solitary confinement, cooped up alone, and then you might say that's how to fix your life, but you don't know if you feel like a man or a woman, or if you're attracted to men or women, or both.

Participant 14

During the interviews, several prevailing stereotypes came to light. One is based on the belief that many transgender people seeking medical care are doing so because of a personality disorder. In such cases, reference is made to transgender women who begin the transition process in a disruptive manner and exhibit self-destructive, impulsive behaviours, and suicidal ideation. Professionals tend to make a direct link between the transgender experience and a possible symptom or effect of personality pathology, overlooking other factors such as environmental support or social determinants of health.

Not only because of the type of surgeries, like butt implants, or even facial surgeries... Everything very brightly colored, a lot of make-up... The clothes were very flashy. Very unruly, both cases were very unruly, very demanding, full of rage... They stood out. They went to the emergency room a lot, for example, they were repeat visitors, like a revolving door

Participant 7

Another stereotype mentioned by professionals involves adolescents with autistic traits who begin to express their gender identity during adolescence. In such cases, professionals tend to attribute the origin of gender diversity to a denial or rejection of their sexuality or to the

development of secondary sexual characteristics. This reflects a tendency to psychologize and pathologize these users, who are often teenage transgender men.

Some girls who, when they reach adolescence and begin to develop feminine characteristics, suddenly reject them and don't want to be that, but it's not like they really wanted to be boys either, they just didn't want... the feminine stuff. And then on further exploration, there were also kind of like Asperger's traits, maybe struggling to understand some things.

Participant 9

3.2 | Theme 2: Attitudes and behaviours of mental health professionals toward transgender people

We proceed from the hypothesis that the attitudes of professionals—their mental, emotional, and behavioural dispositions—will be shaped by the beliefs described earlier. It is important to note that the professionals interviewed exhibited attitudes centred on respect, support, and counselling. They were able to identify specific needs when working with transgender people, including providing emotional support and sensitive counselling throughout the transition process. They also emphasized the importance of raising awareness among the various stakeholders involved in this process and the ability to provide guidance on the resources available in the public mental health network.

You can come up with many work and awareness-raising initiatives, and preventive initiatives in other areas, but I think that, as it's a group, it's essential to have a dedicated program that also involves mental health. I mean, it should be a multidisciplinary team of everyone involved in the process, with the patient front and center, of course, and the family providing support.

Participant 12

Similarly, they have been proactive in identifying training needs in relation to the professional skills and specific resources required to care for and support this community. Professionals often recognize this lack of training as a barrier to access to the healthcare system and relate it to their own insecurities about clinical work with transgender people. They themselves emphasized that the essential skills for working with transgender people include mastering the relevant terminology, knowledge of the applicable legislation, and familiarity with the medical transition process. Some professionals also discussed the possibility of having specialised multidisciplinary units where users can receive care in an environment tailored to their needs. Moreover, some professionals stress the importance of understanding the psychological issues that can arise when working with these users.

Having a dedicated space to deal with these types of cases would be of great benefit because these people must have so many questions... as do the professionals. Keep in mind that we treat these people like any other patient without having specific training, we don't have all the answers...

Participant 7

Overall, most professionals were open to using the correct pronouns, although they admitted to sometimes hesitating to ask users about their identity because of their own insecurities. Furthermore, several professionals stressed the importance of building a strong therapeutic partnership when treating transgender people. This involves addressing instances of exclusion and stigma as an integral part of the therapeutic support provided to these users.

Conversely, alongside these positive attitudes, there were instances of negative and even discriminatory attitudes on the part of some professionals, which could vary in their explicitness. There were instances of professionals stressing the importance of not treating transgender people differently, implying a disregard for the specific needs and unique characteristics of the community.

Well, I think that, when it comes to the physical, biological side of things, it's what any person might be bothered about, right? Like, their health in general. And I get that depending on the age we're talking about, different issues might crop up, you know? Like, I don't know, issues around maternity, all that kind of stuff.

Participant 12

These attitudes and behaviours become more explicit, calling into question the transgender reality and lived experiences of these people. There is also a tendency towards paternalism regarding users' choices, denial of some of their common problems, and even the use of stigmatising and sexist language. Although these attitudes were in the minority, they are part of the reality faced by users within the mental health system.

Well, based on my own experience...I'd kind of see it as a way to find a place in the world, a cry for help, a way to get attention from the professional or someone else.

Participant 3

3.2.1 | Pathologisation

As noted throughout the paper, professionals often make a distinction between transgender people they perceive as 'healthy' and those they perceive as not, and it is the latter group who are most likely to seek help from the mental health system. In these instances,

where users seek help from the mental health system, professionals frequently adopt pathologising attitudes, often arriving at the assumption that gender identity itself is a consequence of an underlying mental health condition. Professionals in these cases may even entertain doubts to the extent of attempting to treat gender expression by addressing the underlying mental condition for which the person is seeking help. When dealing with patients with mental illness, professionals often overlook the possibility that this may also be connected to the stigma and discrimination that people have experienced throughout their lives. Instead, they tend to view gender diversity as a result of the underlying mental condition, attributing psychological causes that can be modified.

And now, well, we are seeing a whole lot of personality disorders which are associated with the trans area, but not genuine trans. Those are the factors that I'm picking up on right now.

Participant 3

Transgender people who have been diagnosed with a personality, psychotic, or autism spectrum disorder may face additional hurdles when it comes to having their gender identity validated by mental health professionals. Such people may be questioned by professionals about their gender identity and subjected to discriminatory attitudes.

So, as far as I can recall, this person had been diagnosed with schizophrenia or some other personality disorder... But, in this particular case, they hadn't undergone surgery or hormone therapy. The hospital's ethics committee got involved in this case because the endocrinology and psychology teams had serious doubts as to whether the medical team as such could refuse the patient's request or if this would violate their rights to want to transition.

Participant 1

For sure, I do see a difference among patients presenting with some kind of mental illness, maladaptive personality traits, and on that basis they get into the whole transgender movement... as it were...or gender identity, this whole movement...

Participant 10

3.2.2 | Attitudes toward decision making

Throughout the interviews, we explored the professionals' attitudes towards transgender people's decision-making during the transition process. Many professionals adopted a supportive mindset, reflecting a largely user-centred approach and recognizing the importance of empowering people in their transition journey, as happens in other healthcare situations.

That is why... you hear people saying 'there needs to be a psychiatric report, which will say whether or not they should go through this process or not'. Well, I put it in inverted commas, because here there's a loss of people's freedom, their rights, about what they want to do with their lives. That they are deluding themselves and making a mistake... Well, that's your call, you are free to make your own decisions...

Participant 7

However, professionals were less confident in cases where the person had a history of prior mental health issues. Their concerns centred on the potential long-term consequences of making hasty decisions about hormone treatment or where mental health conditions could complicate the transition process.

But, you know, the consequence of not involving us is that there's some pathological reason, right? Something in this whole process that goes undetected, isn't taken care of, and keeps on causing discomfort. But, of course, if I'm in the process of transitioning shouldn't I seek the assistance of a professional who is supposed to give me support?

Participant 4

4 | DISCUSSION

Our findings help provide a deeper understanding of the beliefs and attitudes of mental health professionals towards transgender people by examining key factors such as knowledge, beliefs, and stereotypes. These factors play a key role in mediation and clinical interaction between professionals and users.

The findings from our analysis of the interviews suggest that professionals tend to attribute gender diversity to the increased visibility of the LGBTQI+ community and the advances in rights that have been achieved through social activism in recent years (Espinosa, 2020). This oversimplification of the factors behind the transgender experience can lead to pathologising attitudes that tend to marginalize those who do not conform to normative patterns of gender identity (Villafaña & Gómez, 2021). The transgender experience, along with other gender-related variables, is an inherent part of human diversity. Establishing inclusive healthcare spaces is a crucial step towards ensuring the psychological well-being of all users (Delaney & McCann, 2021; García-Acosta et al., 2020). Meanwhile, the inflexibility seen in professionals with respect to the patterns that transgender people must adhere to (e.g., to be considered healthy, they must have rejected their assigned gender since childhood) could be explained by the theory of double stigma (Moore et al., 2021). According to this theory, groups that are already stigmatised due to certain identities face a second level of stigma associated with another area, in this case mental illness (Fernando Cedeño Astudillo, 2019).

Also noteworthy is the recurring theme in professionals' responses regarding their lack of training and perceived lack of knowledge. These results are consistent with previous research using both quantitative methods (Bolding et al., 2022; Martin et al., 2022; Powell & Cochran, 2021) and qualitative approaches (Holt et al., 2020; Soled et al., 2022; Torres et al., 2015), which produced similar results. The onus is on addressing specific training gaps as key opportunities to improve the comprehensive care of all users (Zeeman et al., 2019). In this regard, programmes focused on the dissemination of guidelines and training in standards of care, such as those outlined by Coleman et al. (2022), would serve as useful and powerful tools with which to enhance the knowledge of professionals.

In terms of healthcare needs, professionals generally identify at least one need specific to transgender users, such as hormone treatments, reproductive health, or surgeries. However, most of the needs identified are typically associated with the transition process, and sometimes these healthcare needs are even limited exclusively to this process. The literature reviewed links these problems in identifying needs to a lack of expertise and skills in treating transgender users (Delaney & McCann, 2021; Donisi et al., 2020; Miller et al., 2023). With regard to the transition process, participants are inclined to the view that transgender people should undergo the complete process of gender reassignment via medical and surgical procedures. This attitude among professionals, which has been identified as an obstacle to depathologization in other studies (Carrizo, 2014; Nieder & Richter-Appelt, 2011), oversimplifies a complex process encompassing a wide range of issues, including gender identity, gender expression, and, in some instances, medical intervention (Suess Schwend, 2020). These beliefs on the part of professionals reflect not only ignorance about the concepts of gender identity but also an undercurrent of stigma stemming from the misconceptions that all transgender people must undergo medical procedures in order to live in alignment with their identity and that they desire to be perceived as cisgender (Powell & Cochran, 2021; Puckett et al., 2018; Rodríguez Madera et al., 2019).

In terms of beliefs about transgender users and what they need from the mental health system, certain stereotypes are repeated. This potentially perpetuates stigma towards these users, particularly those who have been diagnosed with a mental health condition. These findings, which indicate the impact of beliefs on professionals' clinical attitudes, have been extensively discussed in the context of other minority groups (e.g. racial minorities) (Ayalon & Gum, 2011; Calabrese et al., 2015). Viewing users through the lens of minority stress theory (Meyer, 2003), which aims to explain how the stressful and discriminatory experiences faced by LGBTIQ individuals in society can negatively affect their mental health (Rivas-Koehl et al., 2023), could lead professionals to adopt a more comprehensive approach when addressing the mental health challenges faced by TGD individuals.

As far as pathologising attitudes are concerned, our findings are in line with previous research that has examined this issue (Brown et al., 2020; Jiménez-Barbero et al., 2023; Kanamori & Cornelius-White, 2016; Soled et al., 2022). However, our study contributes

additional insight by identifying the diagnoses or mental illnesses most commonly reported by professionals.

Finally, on the subject of decision-making by professionals, our results are consistent with other studies that have explored this issue (Holt et al., 2020; Powell & Cochran, 2021; Salpietro et al., 2019). In this regard, professionals' concerns often centre on the potential long-term effects of hormone treatment or situations where mental health conditions may have a mediating effect on the transition process (Friley & Venetis, 2022).

4.1 | Limitations of the study

One of the main limitations of our study is the heterogeneity of the sample obtained. However, despite this, we achieved theoretical saturation of the data early on. This was confirmed by the final interviews, the analysis of which confirmed the results already analysed. Likewise, the limited number of participants means that the results cannot be generalised to all mental health professionals. Despite the limitations of our sample, the beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours described in the results section are supported by the literature reviewed in the discussion section.

4.2 | Implications for clinical practice

Gaining insight into the attitudes of mental health professionals towards transgender people can help improve the quality of health care and reduce the inequalities involved in accessing the health-care system. Our findings indicate that professionals lack training and skills in working with transgender people and highlight the need to include specific content on gender and sexual minorities in the curricula of social and health professions. Continuing education is also essential. This knowledge would be a crucial step towards providing more equitable care that focuses on people's individual needs.

5 | CONCLUSION

Our findings suggest that mental health professionals working in the region of Murcia hold stereotypical beliefs about transgender people that oversimplify the complex nature of this experience. There is evidence that perceptions of gender diversity are oversimplified, which can lead to pathologising attitudes and reducing healthcare needs to the transition process. The lack of training perceived by professionals underscores the need to address these training gaps to improve comprehensive care by including them in the curricula of health and social professions. It also emphasizes the need to challenge deep-seated beliefs that inhibit understanding of gender identity and perpetuate stereotypes, thereby contributing to the stigmatisation of transgender people with mental illness.

6 | REVELANCE STATEMENT

Our study reveals that mental health professionals hold stereotypical beliefs about trans people, oversimplifying the complexity of this experience. These perceptions reduce gender diversity to a transition process and tend to pathologise, ignoring other health care needs. The lack of training identified highlights the urgent need to include specific content on gender minorities and sexuality in health and social professions training, challenging entrenched beliefs that perpetuate stereotypes and stigmatize trans people with mental illness.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors report that are no competing interests to declare.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Due to the confidential nature of the data collected, it is not available to anyone outside the research team.

ETHICS STATEMENTS

The study was approved by the University of Murcia's Ethics Committee (Reg. No. CEI 3123).

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